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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
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05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
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05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
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08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
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08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

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ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOR IN ENTERPRISES AND ITS IMPACT ON MANAGEMENT DECISION-MAKING: A REVIEW OF THEORIES

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Abstract. This article presents an analytical review of organizational development theories from the perspective of the behavioral characteristics of leaders and employees in the process of effective management decision-making. The evolution of theories related to organizational members' behavior and development is briefly examined, and a modern behavioral model of organizational development is scientifically substantiated. The study also analyzes the factors influencing management effectiveness and the successful implementation of organizational change based on game theory approaches.

Keywords: organizational behavior, organizational development, management decision-making, game theory, leadership, motivation, organizational culture.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada samarali boshqaruv qarorlarini qabul qilish jarayonida rahbarlar va xodimlarning xulq-atvor xususiyatlari nuqtayi nazaridan tashkiliy rivojlanish nazariyalari analitik jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Tashkilot a'zolarining xulq-atvori va ularning rivojlanishiga oid nazariyalarning evolyutsiyasi qisqacha ko'rib chiqilib, tashkiliy rivojlanishning zamonaviy xulq-atvor modeli ilmiy asosda yoritilgan. Tadqiqotda game theory yondashuvi asosida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish hamda tashkilotlarda o'zgarishlarni muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirish omillari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: tashkiliy xulq-atvor, tashkiliy rivojlanish, boshqaruv qarorlari, game theory, rahbarlik, motivatsiya, tashkiliy madaniyat.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлен аналитический обзор теорий организационного развития с точки зрения поведенческих особенностей руководителей и сотрудников в процессе принятия эффективных управленческих решений. Проведён краткий анализ эволюции теорий, связанных с поведением членов организации и их развитием, а также научно обоснована современная поведенческая модель организационного развития. В исследовании на основе подходов game theory рассмотрены факторы повышения эффективности управления и успешной реализации организационных изменений.

Ключевые слова: организационное поведение, организационное развитие, управленческие решения, game theory, лидерство, мотивация, организационная культура.

INTRODUCTION

People and organizations operate in an environment characterized by continuous evolutionary development. The modern organizational environment, marked by an unprecedented level of uncertainty and dynamic transformation, establishes new requirements for organizational functioning and sustainable growth. Intensifying competition in the global market, increasing social and environmental responsibilities, unstable financial systems, expanding legal regulations, and the growing demand of consumers for quality, innovation, and convenience, together with rapid technological progress, global telecommunications, international economic integration, and the expansion of mergers, acquisitions, and strategic partnerships, have significantly transformed the contemporary business environment. These interconnected and rapidly evolving factors create a highly dynamic and complex environment for organizations operating in both manufacturing and service sectors, as well as in public and private institutions (Peters, 1987). Under such conditions, organizations seeking sustainable development and long-term competitiveness must continuously adapt to environmental changes.

As noted by Korth (1998), organizations evolve through changes in their structures, missions, objectives, and operational activities, while outdated systems and management approaches necessitate the transition toward more modern and effective organizational forms and management mechanisms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Change has become one of the most important and permanent characteristics of modern organizational life. As emphasized by management scholar Peter Drucker, organizations must either systematically and purposefully transform their existing business models or risk losing competitiveness under the influence of rapidly changing external conditions (Drucker, 1994). In this regard, not only the selection of an appropriate strategic change but also the effective implementation of change management processes plays a decisive role in ensuring organizational sustainability and long-term development. Studies conducted over the past thirty years indicate that nearly 70% of organizational change initiatives fail to achieve their intended objectives (Ewenstein et al., 2015). This demonstrates the complexity of organizational transformation processes and highlights the importance of scientifically grounded management approaches.

From a systems perspective, every organization can be considered an open and interconnected system consisting of multiple internal subsystems. Each subsystem possesses its own inputs, outputs, and functional responsibilities while simultaneously interacting with other organizational components. Based on this approach, organizational interventions are designed according to the problems they address and the organizational levels they influence (Cummings & Worley, 1993). In particular, organizational development interventions are generally associated with four interrelated dimensions: human process issues, technological and structural issues, human resource management issues, and strategic management issues. These dimensions collectively determine organizational effectiveness and require integrated implementation within the organizational development process.

The effectiveness of organizational change is also closely associated with economic and behavioral factors. In this context, the economic efficiency of change largely depends on transaction costs arising within organizational relationships, while the level of these costs is strongly influenced by organizational trust and culture. A strong organizational culture grounded in ethical values and mutual cooperation contributes to reducing resistance to change, strengthening collaboration among organizational members, and increasing overall productivity. Consequently, organizational success is significantly determined by the quality of organizational culture and the effectiveness of interpersonal relations.

Regardless of the scale or complexity of change interventions, employees remain the central participants in the implementation of planned organizational transformations. Therefore, the success of organizational development initiatives depends on the effectiveness of relationships between leaders and employees, as well as the creation of a constructive behavioral climate within the organization. Ineffective communication, inadequate employee involvement, and resistance to organizational transformation may negatively affect even carefully designed change initiatives. Accordingly, understanding the behavioral and economic interactions between organizational participants, anticipating possible managerial challenges, and establishing a cooperative organizational environment are among the most important factors ensuring successful organizational change.

This study primarily relies on concepts developed within organizational development and game theory. Organizational development is understood as a systematic process through which behavioral science knowledge and practical approaches are applied to improve organizational effectiveness, employee productivity, product and service quality, and the overall organizational climate (Drucker, 1994). Planned organizational change differs from unplanned change in that it is implemented according to predefined long-term goals intended to benefit both organizational members and organizational performance. Organizational development methods are therefore aimed at simultaneously improving organizational climate and enhancing organizational performance (Larwood, 1984).

From the perspective of game theory, organizational interactions may be interpreted as economic and behavioral processes involving two or more participants pursuing their own objectives and strategies. In such processes, participants exchange economic or emotional values depending on the outcomes of their interactions. Cooperative games emerge when participants possess full information regarding each other's strategies and expected benefits, whereas non-cooperative games arise under conditions of incomplete information and conflicting interests. Information asymmetry occurs when organizational participants possess unequal levels of knowledge concerning strategic intentions and expected outcomes.

Within the organizational change process, leaders represent managers or managerial groups responsible for initiating and coordinating transformation, while followers represent employees required to adapt their behavior to new organizational norms and objectives. The effectiveness of organizational transformation

depends on multiple behavioral and managerial parameters, including motivation systems, projected organizational growth, leadership expenditures, employee sensitivity, and levels of organizational resistance. These factors collectively determine the current state of organizational change processes and influence the success of strategic transformation initiatives.

Organizational equilibrium can be defined as a state within the organizational system in which organizational benefits and effectiveness are maximized. In this context, equilibrium sensitivity reflects the extent to which the organizational state changes depending on variations in internal and external parameters. Scholars in the field of organizational development identify three fundamental components of organizational development: improving organizational effectiveness, applying principles of humanistic psychology, and utilizing social science approaches in organizational management (Smither ed., 1996). Humanistic psychology assumes that organizations consist of interconnected individuals who possess inherent psychological growth needs and whose development significantly influences organizational performance.

Organizational development, also referred to as planned organizational change management, has become an increasingly important field in modern organizations operating under conditions of intense domestic and global competition. As market systems evolved from domestic to international and subsequently to global forms, organizational development practitioners adapted their approaches to meet emerging organizational requirements (Cummings, 1993). These studies primarily focused on identifying the conditions under which managers and employees could effectively cooperate and thereby improve organizational productivity. Early research findings demonstrated that social relationships and interpersonal communication play a crucial role in determining workplace effectiveness and employee performance (Roethlisberger et al., 1939).

Many organizational development scholars associate the emergence of the organizational development era with laboratory training methods introduced by Kurt Lewin and his colleagues at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. These training methods, commonly known as T-groups or basic skills training groups, became highly influential because they focused on communication processes, interpersonal relations, and group dynamics within organizations (Smither ed., 1996). The experiments conducted through T-group methodologies significantly contributed to understanding employee interaction and collaborative behavior in organizational settings.

To strengthen communication within organizations, feedback-based interventions and survey techniques were introduced as important organizational development tools. In particular, R. Likert conducted extensive research on organizational human processes, including employees' perceptions of supervisors, promotion opportunities, satisfaction with teamwork, managerial behavior, and organizational feedback systems (Likert, 1932; Drucker, 1994). These studies highlighted the importance of employee participation, communication quality, and managerial support in improving organizational effectiveness.

In parallel with action research approaches aimed at implementing organizational change, several management initiatives were developed to improve productivity and the Quality of Work Life (QWL). These approaches were applied to analyze organizational value chains, work systems, and organizational architecture, as well as the relationships between them (Trist, 1951). The practical implementation of QWL programs later contributed to the emergence of the sociotechnical systems approach, according to which every organization consists of interconnected social and technological systems. Consequently, changes introduced into one subsystem inevitably influence the functioning of the other subsystem (Smither ed., 1996). Applied research and sociotechnical approaches were therefore designed to better understand the relationship between employee behavior and the work environment and to support the development of work processes capable of improving employee productivity, satisfaction, and organizational performance. In modern practice, QWL programs have expanded beyond individual workplace issues to include broader organizational dimensions such as reward systems, work processes, leadership styles, and organizational environments, thereby contributing significantly to the enhancement of organizational effectiveness.

Organizational culture is formed through the collective perceptions, beliefs, and values shared by organizational members regarding themselves, customers, competitors, and society. When these beliefs and values are widely accepted throughout the organization, the culture is considered strong and stable (Smither ed., 1996). Organizational culture encompasses accepted behavioral patterns, managerial and subordinate roles, and established organizational norms. Roles define expected patterns of behavior associated with specific positions, while norms regulate interactions and behavioral standards within the organization. A manager, for example, is expected to demonstrate leadership qualities, whereas employees are expected to support organizational transformation processes.

In contemporary organizational development theory, organizational culture is recognized as one of the most influential factors affecting organizational performance and long-term sustainability. At the same time, culture is also regarded as one of the most complex organizational components and a major source of resistance to change because cultural transformation typically occurs gradually over time. According to the sociotechnical

systems perspective, changes introduced into organizational structures or value chains require corresponding changes within the social system, particularly within organizational culture. Strategic change approaches were therefore developed to strengthen the relationship between organizations and their external environments through open systems planning while simultaneously integrating technical, political, and cultural dimensions of organizational management (Beckhard, 1987). Such strategic organizational changes are commonly triggered by significant external or internal developments, including regulatory reforms, technological breakthroughs, or the appointment of new leadership within the organization (Miller, 1980).

Within organizational theory, three major theoretical approaches are widely recognized due to their distinct perspectives on organizational structure and organizational development factors. Bureaucracy theory argues that organizations function most effectively when formal rules, procedures, and regulations are systematically established to govern organizational activities (Weber, 1947). This theory emphasizes organizational structures and standardized procedures that evolve gradually and apply equally to all organizational members. Consequently, organizational change interventions within the bureaucratic framework primarily focus on redesigning organizational structures and work procedures while giving comparatively limited attention to the behavioral role of individuals in implementing organizational transformation processes.

In contrast to bureaucratic theory, the human relations approach emerged from the principles of humanistic psychology developed by scholars such as Maslow (1954), Likert (1961), and McGregor (1960). According to this theoretical perspective, effective interpersonal communication and positive human relations significantly contribute to improving organizational effectiveness. Within this framework, organizational change is viewed as a process similar to individual psychological development, where sustainable and effective transformation occurs primarily at the level of individuals and work groups rather than through rigid top-down managerial control. Consequently, employee motivation, cooperation, participation, and interpersonal trust are regarded as essential factors influencing organizational performance and successful organizational transformation.

Another influential approach in organizational theory is contingency theory, which differs substantially from both bureaucratic and human relations theories. According to contingency theory, organizational effectiveness is not determined solely by organizational structure or human factors; rather, it is strongly influenced by the macroeconomic and external environmental conditions surrounding the organization (Lawrence, 1967). From this perspective, successful organizations are those capable of continuously learning, adapting, and restructuring their organizational culture and management systems in response to changing environmental factors. Advocates of contingency theory emphasize that no universal organizational structure or management model can effectively operate under all conditions. Therefore, each organization must develop flexible and adaptive management mechanisms suited to its specific environment and strategic objectives.

In practical organizational management, enterprises generally apply combinations of bureaucratic, human relations, and contingency approaches throughout different stages of organizational development. Such integration allows organizations to balance structural stability, employee motivation, and environmental adaptability more effectively.

Among the earliest and most influential models of planned organizational change is Kurt Lewin's change model (Lewin, 1951). Lewin conceptualized organizations as behavioral systems influenced by two opposing forces: forces supporting change and forces resisting change in an attempt to preserve the existing organizational state. He described the condition in which these opposing forces remain balanced as a "quasi-stationary equilibrium," where organizational behavior remains relatively stable. Building upon this concept, subsequent planning models attempted to provide a more comprehensive understanding of planned organizational transformation processes (Lippitt eds., 1958). According to the action research model, planned change represents a cyclical process consisting primarily of knowledge generation and the practical implementation of change initiatives (Kolb, 1970).

David Hussey later described change management as a six-stage interconnected process integrating motivational, leadership, and administrative dimensions of organizational transformation (Hussey, 2000). Within this approach, motivational and leadership tasks are aimed at inspiring organizational members, reducing resistance to change, and encouraging active employee participation, whereas administrative tasks focus on improving implementation plans and evaluating organizational outcomes. In this regard, motivational processes and leadership behavior are closely associated with the principles of human relations theory and may also be effectively analyzed using game theory methodologies.

Understanding organizational culture is particularly important for assessing the potential level of resistance that may emerge during organizational change interventions (Harvey, 1988). According to this perspective, resistance to change largely depends on the scale of organizational transformation and the extent to which change initiatives affect existing organizational values, norms, and behavioral patterns. Consequently, organizational culture becomes a central factor influencing the success or failure of organizational development initiatives.

The application of open systems theory (Likert, 1932), systems theory (Thayer, 1974), living systems theory (Vancouver, 1996), chaos theory (Thietart, 1995), complexity theory, and game theory has significantly contributed to the advancement of organizational development practices. Open systems theory conceptualizes planned organizational change as a process aimed at establishing an optimal balance between the organization and its external environment. Within this framework, the concepts of sociotechnical systems (Cummings, 1977), self-organizing organizations (Cummings & Mohrman, 1987), and trans-organizational development (Cummings, 1984) represent important examples of applying systems-based approaches to organizational transformation.

Systems theory further complements open systems planning by viewing organizations and their environments as integrated and interconnected systems composed of multiple subsystems operating at different levels. Each subsystem influences and is influenced by other subsystems within the organizational structure. However, the complete implementation of systems theory in organizational analysis may result in excessive complexity and computational difficulties (Greene, 1999).

Ultimately, even the most advanced organizational structures and sophisticated technologies cannot ensure organizational effectiveness unless organizational members, including both managers and employees, accept and adapt to the designed techno-structural system. At the same time, techno-structural systems must support employees' needs for personal growth, professional development, and organizational participation. Therefore, any technological or structural transformation within an organization should be accompanied by the development of human resources, interpersonal relations, and organizational cooperation mechanisms. In this context, the development of constructive human relations should be regarded as one of the fundamental components of successful planned organizational change.

Since employee motivation and engagement are among the most important factors determining the success of organizational interventions, change leaders must possess a comprehensive understanding of how individuals perceive motivation and respond to managerial influence. In this context, Theory X and Theory Y represent simplified yet influential approaches to employee motivation and managerial behavior. Managers operating under Theory X generally assume that employees are inherently passive, reluctant to accept responsibility, resistant to challenges, and lacking sufficient self-motivation. Consequently, such managers tend to rely primarily on strict supervision, rewards, and punishment mechanisms to regulate employee behavior. This "carrot-and-stick" approach reflects a managerial assumption that employees require continuous external control to maintain productivity (Larwood, 1984). However, such an approach often fails to recognize that employees may possess intrinsic motivational factors similar to those motivating managers themselves. Modern organizational studies increasingly emphasize that employee productivity and organizational commitment are significantly strengthened when employees are treated as active participants in organizational development rather than passive executors of managerial directives.

Transactional analysis represents another important interpersonal intervention approach aimed at improving organizational culture through increasing individuals' awareness of interpersonal communication and behavioral interaction patterns (Berne, 1961). This approach is largely based on the principles of game analysis, which seeks to identify the hidden motives and psychological dynamics underlying interpersonal interactions within organizations (Smither ed., 1996). Within this framework, "games" are understood as covert behavioral interactions that may involve manipulative communication patterns, emotional influence, and attempts to reinforce particular attitudes toward others. Although transactional analysis provides valuable insights into interpersonal behavior and organizational communication, its primary limitation lies in its focus on psychological dimensions of personality without fully incorporating broader economic and organizational factors influencing human behavior.

In recent decades, game theory has gained substantial importance because of its strong compatibility with modern economic methodologies and organizational analysis (Rasmusen, 2002). Scholars applying game theory have expanded traditional transactional analysis into transaction cost analysis, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of organizational interactions. From the perspective of game theory, organizational processes may be interpreted as systems of interaction in which multiple participants pursue distinct objectives through various strategic actions, while organizational outcomes depend on the nature of interactions among participants. In such processes, gains and losses may include both economic and emotional dimensions, allowing researchers to model organizational behavior using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Although emotional considerations influence human behavior, economic motivations frequently play a dominant role in organizational decision-making and strategic interaction.

One of the major advantages of game theory is its flexibility in modeling transactional processes occurring not only between individuals and groups but also across broader socioeconomic systems involving cooperation, competition, negotiation, and strategic adaptation. Consequently, researchers have increasingly applied game theory methods to examine organizational behavior, leadership dynamics, and economic decision-making

processes. For example, Mark Casson analyzed leader–follower interactions and business transactions as forms of strategic exchange while also examining the influence of organizational and national culture on economic behavior (Casson, 1991). Through mathematical and behavioral analysis, Casson demonstrated that cooperative, ethical, and altruistic organizational cultures contribute positively to productivity and economic performance. Similarly, Collard (1981) argued that individuals and organizations benefit more from cooperative and altruistic environments than from excessively individualistic and purely self-interested economic systems. Empirical studies have also shown that altruistic preferences and cooperative behavior can positively influence the efficient provision of public goods and strengthen social and organizational effectiveness (Russell ed., 2003). Such multidimensional analyses are difficult to achieve through traditional techno-structural organizational theories alone.

Furthermore, research on interpersonal transactional processes indicates that employee satisfaction is influenced not only by absolute rewards but also by relative and competitive incentive structures. In particular, comparative perceptions regarding compensation, recognition, and organizational rewards significantly affect employees' job satisfaction, motivation, and social well-being within organizations (Charness & Grosskopf, 2001). These findings suggest that organizational leaders should design motivational systems that balance economic incentives with fairness, cooperation, and positive organizational culture in order to achieve sustainable organizational effectiveness and employee engagement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study is based on a theoretical and analytical approach to organizational behavior and management decision-making processes. The study applies concepts from organizational development theory, systems theory, and game theory to analyze the behavioral interactions between leaders and employees within enterprises. Comparative analysis, conceptual synthesis, and scientific literature review methods were used to evaluate classical and modern organizational theories, including bureaucracy theory, human relations theory, and contingency theory. The research also examines the influence of organizational culture, motivation, and behavioral factors on change management and decision-making effectiveness. Furthermore, the study utilizes a systems-based analytical framework to identify the interdependence between organizational structures, employee behavior, and environmental factors in achieving organizational effectiveness and sustainable development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Numerous factors influence organizational effectiveness; however, one of the most significant determinants is individual employee behavior (Smither et al., 1996). Research in the field of organizational architecture demonstrates that organizations generally pursue two fundamental outcomes: improving organizational effectiveness and supporting individual development (Porras & Robertson, 1992). These outcomes are largely shaped by workplace behavior, which is influenced by employees' individual thinking patterns, organizational norms, technological systems, interpersonal relations, personality-specific characteristics, and external environmental factors. In this context, organizational vision plays a critical role in shaping and coordinating the internal organizational environment to ensure consistency between strategic objectives and employee behavior.

The change-oriented organizational structure model presented by Porras et al. (1992) illustrates the interdependence between the internal and external environments of an organization within a holistic systems framework. According to this approach, organizational effectiveness cannot be achieved solely through structural or technological improvements; rather, it requires the harmonious integration of organizational culture, employee behavior, leadership practices, and environmental adaptation mechanisms. Therefore, sustainable organizational development depends on the organization's ability to coordinate internal processes effectively while simultaneously responding flexibly to dynamic external conditions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A change-based organizational framework.

This model identifies organizational behavior as one of the most important factors influencing organizational performance and the achievement of strategic outcomes. However, the model pays relatively limited attention to the role of leadership as a key factor shaping organizational behavior and guiding organizational transformation processes. Building upon these ideas, organizational development specialists and change agents should consider organizations as integrated systems composed of interdependent subsystems. Consequently, changes introduced in one organizational component are highly likely to influence other areas of the organization. Since organizations function as open systems, human behavior develops within the framework

of established organizational norms, rules, and institutional structures while simultaneously interacting with internal organizational processes and external environmental factors, including national culture, economic conditions, and broader social influences.

In this context, employees become the central focus of organizational development initiatives because organizational change cannot be successfully implemented without their active participation and support. At the same time, employees often represent the primary source of resistance to organizational transformation due to uncertainty, psychological concerns, or perceived risks associated with change. Nevertheless, employees are also the organizational stakeholders most directly affected by both the successes and failures of organizational development interventions. Therefore, effective organizational transformation requires the development of appropriate leadership behavior, constructive interpersonal relations, and management approaches capable of supporting employee adaptation and organizational cooperation.

A number of experimental studies conducted within small-scale societies have provided convincing evidence that prosocial norms, including fairness, reciprocity, and cooperation, tend to strengthen as market integration increases. The underlying logic of this relationship is particularly significant. As markets expand and become more integrated, traditional social control mechanisms characteristic of small communities gradually weaken, thereby increasing the potential for opportunistic behavior. In response to these conditions, market participants seeking mutual economic benefits increasingly encourage fairness, reciprocity, and cooperative behavior in their interactions with others while simultaneously discouraging unfair or opportunistic conduct. Consequently, greater market integration may contribute to the strengthening of prosocial norms toward strangers and unrelated exchange participants (Boyd et al., 2005; Henrich et al., 2006; Henrich et al., 2010).

However, studies examining market integration have often concentrated primarily on the role of informal institutions, such as social enforcement mechanisms and community norms, in regulating exchange relationships within relatively simple societies (Smither et al., 1996). In contrast, broader institutional and organizational dimensions of prosocial behavior in more complex market systems require further investigation.

Various scholars have presented empirical evidence demonstrating that social norms related to fairness, reciprocity, honesty, and ethical behavior function as important counterbalances to purely self-interested motivations. For instance, studies of economic behavior have shown that individuals frequently demonstrate fairness in everyday interactions, such as leaving gratuities in restaurants or taxis regardless of the likelihood of future interaction (Peng, 2003). Experimental research within behavioral economics has similarly demonstrated that participants in ultimatum game experiments typically offer 40–50% of available resources, while extremely unequal offers are often rejected by recipients despite the potential economic loss involved (Camerer, 2003). Furthermore, dictator game experiments reveal that individuals frequently choose to share resources voluntarily even when recipients possess no ability to reject proposed distributions (Forsythe et al., 1994).

Additional studies have also identified manifestations of honesty and prosocial behavior in practical social and economic contexts, including accurate tax reporting (Wenzel, 2004), returning lost wallets to authorities (West, 2005), voluntarily disclosing accounting discrepancies beneficial to oneself (Frank et al., 1993), and returning lost letters containing money to their rightful owners (Zsolnay, 2003). These findings collectively raise an important theoretical question regarding whether prosocial behavior becomes stronger or weaker in highly market-oriented economies.

Several theoretical arguments support the assumption that fairness, reciprocity, and honesty may become even stronger in market-oriented economies characterized by more developed institutional systems. One of the key objectives of game-based behavioral analysis at both national and organizational levels is to examine the extent to which prosocial behavior develops under different market conditions. First, modern large-scale markets involve interactions that are often temporary, anonymous, and less dependent on traditional social relationships (Platteau, 2000). Under such conditions, fairness and honesty toward strangers become increasingly important for sustaining trust and facilitating efficient economic exchange despite weaker direct monitoring and social enforcement mechanisms (Kandori, 1992). Second, by incorporating formal institutions that evolve alongside expanding market systems, researchers can examine whether advanced institutional frameworks strengthen or potentially replace informal prosocial norms within organizational and economic relationships (Bowles et al., 1997; Frey & Oberholzer-Gee, 1997; Reeson & Tisdell, 2008).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study develops a distinct theoretical approach to modeling and the sequential digital transformation of management and decision-making processes in organizational development by incorporating the behavioral parameters of managerial strategies and employee behavior within the framework of game theory methodology. The proposed approach emphasizes the importance of integrating behavioral, organizational, and strategic

dimensions into modern management systems in order to improve organizational effectiveness and support sustainable organizational transformation.

The theoretical analysis conducted in this study, together with the proposed approaches to the digital transformation of decision-making processes, demonstrates that various dimensions of enterprise and industry management can be effectively modeled and integrated into modern digital decision-making systems. These dimensions include predictive and prescriptive business process models, organizational behavior, leadership practices, and socio-cultural management processes. The findings indicate that the application of game theory, systems thinking, and behavioral analysis can significantly enhance the adaptability, efficiency, and strategic responsiveness of organizations operating in dynamic economic environments.

Based on the results of the study, it is recommended that enterprises strengthen organizational culture and improve behavioral management mechanisms in order to increase the effectiveness of managerial decision-making and overall organizational performance. Managers are encouraged to apply modern organizational development approaches, including game theory methodologies and systems-based management principles, to better understand employee behavior, minimize organizational resistance to change, and improve cooperation within organizations. Furthermore, organizations should actively implement digital decision-making systems, strengthen transparent communication between managers and employees, and expand professional development programs focused on leadership, motivation, teamwork, and organizational collaboration. The implementation of these measures can contribute to sustainable organizational development, increased organizational resilience, and improved adaptability to rapidly changing market conditions and technological transformations.

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